

ALTERNATING CURRENT ELECTROLYSIS. PART V. FORMATION OF CHLORATE AND HYPOCHLORITE DURING A.C. ELECTROLYSIS OF HOT SODIUM CHLORIDE SOLUTIONS

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Electrolysis of saturated solution of sodium chloride at 70°, using platinum electrodes with symmetrical alternating current, has been carried out under various conditions of frequency, current density and p_H , using $K_2Cr_2O_7$ as a depolariser.

It is observed that increasing the frequency of alternation, the current efficiency of chlorate as well as hypochlorite formation decreases, so much so that at high frequencies no hypochlorite is detected. With higher current densities, the current efficiency of chlorate as well as hypochlorite formation increases as against the fact that in D.C. electrolysis, the current efficiency of hypochlorite formation decreases with current density. Addition of HCl to the electrolyte has been found to decrease the current efficiency of chlorate formation while in D.C. electrolysis, it increases with the addition of HCl. Hypochlorite efficiency also decreases with the addition of HCl for A.C. as well as in D.C. electrolysis.

Explanation of the observed phenomena, based on recombination reactions taking place at the electrodes, has been offered.

This investigation is in continuation of our previous work on A.C. electrolysis (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 69; 1954, 3, 275)

The production of chlorate and hypochlorite in D.C. electrolysis has been investigated in detail by several workers (Foerster and Dolch, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1917, 23, 137; Foerster and Jorre, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1899, 59, 53; Müller, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1899, 5, 469) and the process is worked on a commercial basis also. It has been shown that in neutral and alkaline solutions, chlorate formation takes place by electrochemical oxidation of ClO^- , discharged at the anode, the ClO^- being produced by the combination of Cl_2 and NaOH, formed at the anode and cathode respectively :

In acid solutions, however, the current efficiency is much greater as the production of chlorate can take place in the entire electrolyte according to

It was therefore thought that by using NaCl as the electrolyte in A.C. electrolysis, current efficiency of chlorate formation would give an idea of different combination and discharge reactions taking place at or near the electrode.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental arrangement was the same as that used in previous investigations (*loc. cit.*).

The electrolyte contained 300 g. of NaCl and 3 g. of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ per litre. NaCl used was Merck's reagent quality, purified by recrystallisation. Polished platinum electrodes, measuring 2 × 2 cms., were used.

The electrolyte (500 c.c.) was taken for each run of electrolysis. The temperature of the electrolyte was maintained at $70^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$. For comparison, an exactly similar cell was placed in the D.C. portion of the circuit. For each experiment, the electrodes were cleaned with HNO_3 (hot, conc.), washed with water and heated to redness before use.

Hypochlorite was estimated against standard sodium arsenite, using starch and KI as external indicator. Chlorate was estimated by adding an excess of KI to the solution and heating in sealed bottles (Vogel, "Quantitative Analysis", p. 423). Iodine liberated was titrated against standard thiosulphate. By subtracting equivalent hypochlorite titre, the amount of chlorate could be evaluated. Distance between the electrodes was always 7 cms. The electrolyte was not stirred.

TABLE I

Effect of frequency on the current efficiency of chlorate and hypochlorite formation.

Platinum electrodes: 8 sq. cm. Current = 1 amp. Amp. hrs. passed = 4.

Frequency per sec.	% C.E. of ClO_3^- formation.		% C.E. of ClO^- formation.	
	D.C.	A.C.	D.C.	A.C.
5	47.96	12.81	36.70	9.95
10	58.30	6.32	37.54	8.10
20	59.40	5.98	37.00	6.18
30	54.70	3.10	27.00	1.50
40	55.05	1.05	24.70	Nil
50	54.80	0.60	21.10	Nil

C.E. denotes current efficiency.

From Table I the current efficiency of chlorate formation in A.C. electrolysis appears to fall with the frequency of alternation, and at higher frequencies it nearly falls to zero. This is also the case with the hypochlorite formation during A.C. electrolysis. At high frequencies, amount of hypochlorite formed in solution is zero. The efficiency in A.C. electrolysis even at as low a frequency as 5 per second is only about $\frac{1}{4}$ th the current efficiency in direct current electrolysis.

TABLE II

Effect of current density on the current efficiency of chlorate and hypochlorite formation.

Platinum electrodes: 8 sq. cm. Ampere hours passed = 4.

C.D. (ma/sq.cm.)	% C.E. of ClO_3^-		% C.E. of ClO^-		C.D. (ma/sq.cm.)	C.E. of ClO_3^-		C.E. of ClO^-	
	D.C.	A.C.	D.C.	A.C.		D.C.	A.C.	D.C.	A.C.
Frequency = 10 per second.					Frequency = 40 per second.				
250.	58.30	6.32	37.54	8.1	250	55.05	6.05	24.70	0.0
500	70.50	22.18	27.14	11.1	500	62.16	8.46	24.06	1.6
750	71.03	29.44	23.15	10.05	750	88.80	30.80	4.60	1.6
					1000.	84.10	38.30	1.00	17.6

C.D. denotes current density.

In A.C. electrolysis, the C.D. plays an important part. The C.E. of chlorate as well as hypochlorite formation increases with C.D. It is significant that the efficiency of hypochlorite formation decreases with C.D. in D.C. electrolysis as against the observed increase during A.C. electrolysis. Another point that is of importance is that by using fairly high current densities, chlorate yield in A.C. electrolysis can be as high as 38% or more.

TABLE III

Effect of addition of 1.58 N-HCl to the electrolyte.

Frequency = 10 per sec. C.D. = 500 ma/sq. cm.

Ampere hours passed = 4. Electrodes : platinum.

HCl added to 500 c.c. of electrolyte.	% C.E. of ClO ₃ .		% C.E. of ClO ⁻ .	
	D.C.	A.C.	D.C.	A.C.
0 c.c.	70.5	27.15	22.18	11.10
5	71.3	23.20	10.40	11.00
10	72.3	80.18	8.10	10.60
20	75.8	15.29	7.45	10.20
25	78.6	12.18	6.73	9.02
30	80.6	10.21	6.32	8.84
40	82.34	8.11	5.86	8.00

Thus, addition of HCl diminishes the yield of chlorate in A.C. electrolysis as against the increased production of chlorate in D.C. electrolysis. The hypochlorite formation shows a rapid decrease with the addition of HCl in D.C. electrolysis; with A.C., however, hypochlorite formation is not appreciably affected.

DISCUSSION

During A.C. electrolysis of NaCl solution, hydrogen and alkali are formed during the cathodic half-cycle and chlorine is evolved during anodic half-cycle. If we assume that the evolution of hydrogen can take place only after the complete saturation of the electrode surface with molecular hydrogen, it is likely that a portion of the hydrogen, discharged during the previous half-cycle, may still be on the electrode surface when chlorine discharge takes place. Hence, recombination reactions that can take place may be :

As the frequency is increased, the duration of each half-cycle becomes smaller, and hence, the primary discharge products, discharged on the electrode, have very little time either to evolve as gas or combine or diffuse into the bulk of the solution, with the result that recombination of discharged products at the electrodes becomes more predominant than the other electrode reactions, leading to the formation of chlorate

or hypochlorite. Thus, we find at a frequency of 50 cycles, there is no hypochlorite in solution, while the chlorate efficiency is as low as 0.6%.

The increase in current efficiency of chlorate formation with increase in C.D. as also the slight increase of C.E. of hypochlorite formation with C.D. in A.C. electrolysis are understandable on the basis of the theory proposed (*vide supra*). At higher C.D. in a given interval of time, the amount of the discharged product round and near the electrode is much larger so that a high concentration of these discharged products exists on and in the vicinity of the electrode surface. As a result of this, the velocity of diffusion of these products into the bulk of the solution is greater. It is not to be understood that the diffusion of products will predominate over recombination reactions. The amount diffusing would always be small since the duration of one half-cycle is of the order of $1/10$ sec. or smaller. The recombination reactions predominate in those cases where high current densities are employed, but the gradual increase in the hypochlorite concentration in the bulk of the solution as a result of diffusion may bring about the formation of chlorate (as in D.C. electrolysis) according to reaction (3).

The addition of H^+ ions to the electrolyte is shown to have quite the reverse effect with respect to chlorate formation as against the observed increase in C.E. in D.C. electrolysis. In the latter case, chlorate is produced by the oxidation of ClO^- by free $HClO$, which in turn is produced by H^+ from added mineral acid and ClO^- , formed at the electrode. This reaction in D.C. electrolysis is known to take place in the bulk of the electrolyte as H^+ ions are liberated as a result of this reaction. In A.C. electrolysis, the addition of H^+ to the solution removes the ClO^- as undissociated $HClO$ so that the concentration of ClO^- in the vicinity of the electrode decreases resulting in the depletion of ClO^- at the electrode, and the discharge of Cl^- during anodic cycle predominates over the ClO^- discharge. Thus, the oxidation of ClO^- according to reaction (2) diminishes with the addition of a strong acid like HCl . Any small ClO^- concentration in the solution will combine with $HClO$, resulting in the formation of chlorate during reaction (3). Thus, the ClO^- efficiency diminishes as increasing amount of acid is added in A.C. electrolysis.

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